

Risk Factors of Stunting in 2-5 years old age in Primary Health Care, Ubud, Gianyar

Ni Kadek Ratih Riska Yanti^{*1}, Komang Triyani Kartinawati², I Wayan Darwata³

¹Student of Faculty of Medicine and Health Science, Warmadewa University

^{2,3}Department of Public Health Health and Preventive Medicine, Faculty of medicine and Health Science, Warmadewa University

*Corresponding email: Ni Kadek Ratih Riska Yanti. ratihriskaa00@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: Stunting is a chronic nutritional disease caused by inadequate nutritional intake during the growth period. The diagnosis of stunting is made if the Z-score of length or height per age is less than -2 SD (Standard Deviation) based on the WHO child growth standard. Purpose: This study aims to explain the factors influences stunting in children aged 2-5 years. This research was carried out in the working area of the Ubud 1 Health Center, Gianyar in January-June 2022. **Methods:** This study was a quantitative analytic study with a case-control design, which used 60 samples, consisting of 30 cases and controls using consecutive sampling. Data was collected by measuring height, interviews and filling out questionnaires. The research was analyzed by univariate, bivariate, and multivariate. **Results:** Based on the Chi-square test, there was a significant relationship between the level of feeding patterns (p-value 0.038), exclusive breastfeeding pattern (p-value 0.000), parental education (p-value 0.001), infectious diseases (p-value 0.019). However the utilization of health services could not be measured in this study. **Conclusion:** This study concluded that the nonexclusive breastfeeding pattern was the most influential factor in the incidence of stunting compared to other risk factors (odds ratio = 9,333). Further research is needed with a mixed method approach in order to obtain better analytical results in assessing the effect on stunting.

Keywords: Stunting, Children 2-5 Years, Risk Factors, Case-Control

INTRODUCTION

Stunting is a chronic nutritional disorder caused by inadequate nutritional intake during the growth and development phase, characterized by a child's height or length that does not correspond to their age.¹ Stunting in children requires special attention as it can lead to impaired physical growth, mental development, and overall health status.² In 2017, the global prevalence of stunting among children was 22.2%, with the highest prevalence in Asia at 55%. According to WHO, Indonesia ranked third in the South-East Asian Region in 2017, with a stunting prevalence of 36.4%, following Timor Leste (50.5%) and India (38.4%).³ The prevalence of stunting in Bali Province is

still considered good, with 20.6% in 2015, categorized as a mild issue (20-30%), 19.7% in 2016, categorized as good (<20%), 19.1% in 2017, and 21.7% in 2018.⁴ The subdistrict with the highest prevalence of stunting is Ubud (28.6%), followed by Gianyar (28.4%), Tegallalang (27.2%), Tampaksiring (26.5%), Blahbatuh (20.4%), Sukawati (12.9%), and Payangan (12.5%). In Ubud Subdistrict, the proportion of stunted children is 23.2%, while severely stunted children account for 5.4%.⁴ The causes of stunting are highly complex and multifactorial. One factor related to stunting is the insufficient provision of exclusive breastfeeding, even though breast milk contains the nutrients most

suited for a baby's growth and development.⁵ Another factor influencing stunting is improper feeding practices, which can result in suboptimal nutrient intake in children. According to Setiawan et al. (2018), children born to educated parents tend to not experience stunting compared to those born to parents with lower education levels. The purpose of this study is to identify the factors influencing stunting in children aged 2-5 years in the working area of Ubud 1 Gianyar Public Health Center.

METHODS

This study was conducted at Ubud 1 Gianyar Public Health Center in September-October 2021. The research method is quantitative analytical using a case-control design. There are two sample groups in this study: case and control, with different inclusion and exclusion criteria between the groups. The study subjects consisted of 60 children obtained from the Lemeshow formula, with each group comprising 30 children aged 2-5 years, with the criteria of being cared for by their mother, residing in the working area of Ubud 1 Gianyar Public Health Center, and having stunted or severely stunted height based on the WHO Child Growth Standard. The research instruments consisted of a questionnaire containing questions about exclusive breastfeeding, recurrent

infections in children, feeding patterns, parents' education level, and healthcare utilization, as well as a Microtoise tool to measure height, which was then converted into standardized values (Z-scores). The sampling technique used was consecutive sampling. The control sample in this study was children with normal height, while the case sample was children who were stunted. The collected data were processed using SPSS version 22 with univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis, along with validity and reliability tests.

RESULTS

Respondent Characteristics

This study was conducted at Ubud 1 Gianyar Public Health Center in September-October 2021. The data were obtained through direct clinical height measurement and questionnaire responses. Table 1 shows that the majority of the study subjects were male, and most were 3 years old. Regarding feeding patterns, most respondents provided proper feeding patterns (45.0%). Regarding exclusive breastfeeding, the majority did not provide exclusive breastfeeding (55.0%). Regarding education, the majority of respondents had a low education level (60.0%). All respondents (100.0%) utilized healthcare services well. Most respondents' children did not experience recurrent infections (56.7%).

Table 1. Characteristic Subject

Variabel	Frekuensi	Persentase
Sex		
Man	33	55,0
Woman	27	45,0
Age		
2 yo	18	30,0
3 yo	26	43,3
4 yo	16	26,7
Dietary pattern		
Inappropriated	33	55,0
Appropriated	27	45,0
ASI Eksklusif		
No	33	55,0

Variabel	Frekuensi	Persentase
Yes	27	45,0
Educational Level		
Low	36	60,0
High	24	40,0
Health Care		
Inappropriated	0	0,0
Appropriated	60	100,0
Repeated Infection		
Yes	26	43,3
No	34	56,7
Total	60	100,0

Relationship Between Eating Patterns and Stunting Incidence

The relationship between eating patterns

and stunting incidence can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: The Relationship Between Eating Patterns and Stunting Incidence

Variabel Diet Pattern	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	Total	<i>P</i> value	OR	CI 95%
Inappropriated	21 (63,6)	12 (36,4)	33	0,038	3,500	1,201 – 10,196
Appropriated	9 (33,3)	18 (66,7)	27			

Based on the table above, it was found that the majority of respondents with improper eating patterns experienced stunting, accounting for 63.6%. The Chi-Square test p-value for the eating pattern variable was 0.038 (p-value < 0.05), indicating that eating patterns have a significant influence on the incidence of

stunting. The OR value of 3.500 shows that respondents with improper eating patterns are 3.5 times more likely to experience stunting compared to respondents with proper eating patterns.

Relationship Between Exclusive Breastfeeding and Stunting Incidence

The relationship between exclusive breastfeeding and stunting incidence can be seen in Table 3.

Variabel Asi Eksklusif	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	Total	<i>P</i> value	OR	CI 95%
No	24 (72,7)	9 (27,3)	33	0,000	9,333	2,287 – 30,602
Yes	6 (22,2)	21 (77,8)	27			

Respondents who did not provide exclusive breastfeeding mostly experienced stunting, with 72.7% of respondents affected. The p-value from the test conducted on the independent variable of exclusive breastfeeding was 0.000 (p-value < 0.05), indicating that exclusive breastfeeding has a significant influence on the incidence of stunting. The

OR value of 9.333 shows that respondents who did not provide exclusive breastfeeding are 9.333 times more likely to experience stunting compared to those who provided exclusive breastfeeding.

Relationship Between Education and Stunting Incidence

The relationship between education and stunting incidence can be seen in Table 4

Table 4. Relationship Between Education and Stunting Incidence

Education Level	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	Total	P value	OR	CI 95%
Low	25 (69,4)	11 (30,6)	36	0,001	8,636	2,566 – 29,073
High	5 (20,8)	19 (79,2)	24			

The majority of respondents with low maternal education levels experienced stunting, accounting for 69.4% of respondents. The p-value from the Chi-Square test for the education variable was 0.001 (p-value < 0.05), indicating that maternal education has a significant influence on the incidence of stunting. The OR value of 8.636 shows that respondents with middle maternal education are 8.636

times more likely to experience stunting compared to respondents with high maternal education.

Relationship Between Recurrent Infections and Stunting Incidence

The relationship between recurrent infections and stunting incidence can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Relationship Between Infections and Stunting Incidence

Variabel Infection	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	Total	P value	OR	CI 95%
Yes	18 (69,2)	8 (30,8)	26	0,019	4,125	1,387 – 12,270
No	12 (35,3)	22 (64,7)	34			

Respondents with a history of recurrent infections mostly experienced stunting, accounting for 69.2%. The p-value from the Chi-Square test for the recurrent infection variable was 0.019 (p-value < 0.05), indicating that the incidence of recurrent infections significantly influences the occurrence of stunting. The OR value of 4.125 shows that respondents with a history of recurrent infections are

4.125 times more likely to experience stunting compared to respondents without a history of recurrent infections.

Relationship Between Healthcare Utilization and Stunting Incidence

The relationship between healthcare utilization and stunting incidence could not be assessed because all study subjects had utilized healthcare services effectively (p = not defined).

Table 6. Odds Ratio

No	Variabel	Odds Ratio f(OR)
1	ASI	9,333
2	Education Levelf	8,636
3	Infection	4,125
4	Feeding pattern	3,500
5	Primary Health Care	-

Based on the bivariate analysis above, it can be concluded that:

1. The factors influencing the incidence of stunting are parental education, exclusive breastfeeding, history of infections, and feeding patterns, as indicated by p-values < 0.05.

2. The most significant risk factor for the incidence of stunting is exclusive breastfeeding, which reduces the risk by 9.333 times for causing stunting in children.

Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis was conducted to determine which factors have the greatest influence on the incidence of stunting.

This analysis was performed based on the bivariate analysis, where the independent

variables used must meet the criteria of p-values < 0.05.

Table 7. Results of Multivariate Analysis of Independent Variables on the Incidence of Stunting

Variabel	Koef. fB	Nilai fp	OR f(95% fCI)
Diet Pattern			
Inapropriated	0,805	0,250	2,237 f (0,568 f– f8,816)
Appropriated			
ASI Eksklusif			
No	1,584	0,025	4,877 f (1,224 f– f19,434)
Yes			
Education level			
Medium	1,796	0,022	6,027 (1,296 f– f28,026)
High			
Repeated Infectio			
Yes	1,517	0,047	4,557 (1,017 f– f20,416)
No			

Based on the results of the multivariate analysis above, it shows that the p-value from the binary logistic regression analysis for the independent variables of exclusive breastfeeding, education, and recurrent infections is less than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that these variables have a significant partial effect on the incidence of stunting.

Discussion

The Influence of Feeding Patterns on the Incidence of Stunting

The results of this study found that among children experiencing stunting, the majority had inappropriate feeding patterns. The analysis shows that there is a relationship between feeding patterns and the incidence of stunting ($p < 0.05$). The odds ratio of 3.500 indicates that children who receive inappropriate feeding patterns are 3.5 times more likely to experience stunting than children who receive adequate feeding. This finding is supported by research conducted by Femidio (2020) in Probolinggo, Central Java. A case-control study involving 46 respondents aimed to determine the differences in feeding patterns and nutritional adequacy in stunted and non-stunted toddlers, concluding that there is a

relationship between feeding patterns and the incidence of stunting ($p = 0.002$).

However, a study by Herianti (2017) in East Jakarta showed contradictory results. The cross-sectional study involving 60 respondents aimed to identify risk factors for stunting in toddlers in the Cipinang Melayu health center area found no relationship between feeding patterns and the incidence of stunting ($p = 0.260$). The differences in findings between this study and the previous two studies may be attributed to variations in the research design used. Nevertheless, the research conducted by the authors using a case-control design is deemed better for determining causal relationships compared to a cross-sectional design. Additionally, there are differences in the questions in the questionnaires used.

The Relationship Between Exclusive Breastfeeding and the Incidence of Stunting

This study found that all children experiencing stunting did not receive exclusive breastfeeding. The analysis shows a relationship between the factor of exclusive breastfeeding and the incidence of stunting ($p < 0.000$). The p-value < 0.05 indicates that exclusive breastfeeding is a

significant factor influencing the incidence of stunting. Moreover, the bivariate analysis shows an odds ratio of 9.333, indicating that toddlers who do not receive exclusive breastfeeding are 9.333 times more likely to be at risk of experiencing stunting compared to those who do.

Another study conducted by Sinambela (2020) in Banjarmasin, South Kalimantan, with a cross-sectional design involving 47 toddlers, found that 34 toddlers experienced stunting. From interviews with the mothers, it was discovered that the mothers and families did not understand the importance of exclusive breastfeeding during their child's growth period. Among the 32 stunted toddlers, they were all non-recipients of exclusive breastfeeding.

Similar findings were reported in a study by Hanifa (2017) in Yogyakarta. A cross-sectional study involving 66 respondents found that 75.8% of stunted children had a history of not receiving exclusive breastfeeding. The analysis also showed a relationship between the history of exclusive breastfeeding and the incidence of stunting ($p < 0.05$).

Breast milk is the best food for infants due to its emulsion of fat, protein, lactose, and inorganic salts, providing a complete source of nutrients according to the primary needs for the first six months of life. In addition, breast milk contains antibodies that can inhibit the growth of pathogenic microbes and pose no risk of allergies.

The Influence of Education on the Incidence of Stunting

The results of this study indicate that among children experiencing stunting, the majority have parents with junior high and high school education. The bivariate analysis shows an odds ratio of 8.636, indicating that children whose parents have low education are at 8.636 times greater risk of experiencing stunting

compared to those with parents who have higher education levels.

According to Apriluana & Fikawati (2018) in a literature review, similar findings were observed. The literature review using the PRISMA method found that low maternal education significantly influences the incidence of stunting in children, with a risk of experiencing stunting 1.67 times. These results are consistent with a study by Setiawan et al. (2018) in Padang, West Sumatra, which found a meaningful relationship between maternal education levels and the incidence of stunting.

However, the findings differ from a study by Ni'mah & Nadhiroh (2016) in Bojonegoro, East Java. This study, involving 47 toddlers from poor families, found no relationship between parental education levels and the incidence of stunting. The differences in findings between this study and the previous three may be attributed to the research designs used. The studies by Apriluana, Setiawan, and Ni'mah utilized cross-sectional designs, while this study employed a case-control design, which is more effective for determining causal relationships. Additionally, there are differences in respondent characteristics among the three studies.

The Influence of Infections on the Incidence of Stunting

This study found that among children experiencing stunting, the majority had infections. The analysis showed a p-value < 0.05 with an odds ratio of 4.125. This indicates a relationship between the infection factor and the incidence of stunting, meaning that toddlers with infections are 4.125 times more likely to experience stunting than those without infections. These findings differ from a study by Fatimah (2018) in Surabaya, East Java, which found no relationship between diarrhea and respiratory infections with the incidence of stunting ($p > 0.05$). However, they align with a study by

Angkat (2018) in Aceh, which found a relationship between the history of infections and stunting in children aged 12-36 months.

Theoretically, children with infections, whether respiratory infections or diarrhea, may experience metabolic disruptions in their bodies due to inflammation from the infections. Initially utilized nutrition for growth may shift functions to enhance immunity against inflammatory reactions. Additionally, various pro-inflammatory cytokines may directly affect chondrocytes, thereby disrupting bone growth and formation processes.

The Influence of Health Service Utilization on the Incidence of Stunting

This study found that all children (both stunted and non-stunted) had parents who had effectively utilized health services. Hypothesis testing could not be performed as all study subjects had adequately utilized health services ($p = \text{undefined}$). This differs from a study conducted by Rhamadani (2020) in Semarang, Central Java, which found a relationship between health service utilization and stunting ($p = 0.007$).

Contrasting results were found in a study by Batubara (2019) in South Tapanuli, North Sumatra, which indicated that health service utilization does not influence the incidence of stunting ($p = 0.829$). Health service utilization is not only practiced when children are sick, but also includes health checks, immunizations, screenings, and early detection of growth and developmental disorders every month. This must be monitored periodically by health personnel.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it was found that feeding patterns, exclusive breastfeeding, education level, and history of recurrent infections influence the incidence of stunting in children aged 2-5 years at the Ubud I Community Health

Center, Gianyar ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The bivariate analysis indicated that the low coverage of exclusive breastfeeding is the most dominant factor influencing the incidence of stunting in the working area of Ubud I Community Health Center, Gianyar ($OR = 9.333$).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my gratitude to my thesis supervisor, examiners, academic advisors, and friends who have provided suggestions and input in completing this writing.

REFERENCES

1. Leroy fJL, fFrongillo fEA. fPerspective: fWhat fDoes fStunting fReally fMean? fA fCritical fReview fof fthe fEvidence. f*Advances fin fNutrition*. f2019;10(2):196-204. fh^{https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nm y101}
2. Setiawan fE, fMachmud fR, fMasrul fM. fFaktor-Faktor fyang fBerhubungan fdengan fKejadian fStunting fpada fAnak fUsia f24-59 fBulan fdi fWilayah fKerja fPuskesmas fAndalas fKecamatan fPadang fTimur fKota fPadang fTahun f2018. f*Jurnal fKesehatan fAndalas*. f2018;7(2):275. fh^{https://doi.org/10.25077/jka.v7.i2.p2 75-284.2018 f}
3. Kemenkes fRI. fBuletin fStunting. f*Kementeri fKesehat fRI*. f2018;301(5):1163-1178.
4. Dinas fKesehatan fProvinsi fBali. fProfil fKesehatan fProvinsi fBali f2018. f*Dinas fKesehat fProvinsi fBali*. fPublished fonline2019:1-129. fh^{https://www.diskesbaliprov.go.id}
5. Apriluana fG, fFikawati fS. fAnalisis fFaktor-Faktor fRisiko fterhadap fKejadian fStunting fpada fBalita f(0-59 fBulan) fdi fNegara fBerkembang fdan fAsia fTenggara. f*Media fPenelitian fdan fPengembangan fKesehatan*. f2018;28(4):247-256.

- <https://doi.org/10.20473/mgi.v13i2.168-175>
6. Femidio fM, fMuniroh fL. fPerbedaan fPola fAsuh fdan fTingkat fKecukupan fZat fGizi fpada fBalita fStunting fdan fNon-Stunting fdi fWilayah fPesisir fKabupaten fProbolinggo. fAmerta fNutrition.2020;4(1):49. <https://doi.org/10.20473/amnt.v4i1.2020.49-57>
 7. Herianti fF, fElwindra. fAnalisis fFaktor fRisiko fKejadian fStunting fPada fAnak fBalita fdi fWilayah fPuskesmas fKelurahan fCipinang fMelayu fJakarta fTimur. fPersada fHusada fIndonesia. f2017;4(14):74-83. <http://jurnal.stikesphi.ac.id/index.php/Kesehatan/article/view/132>
 8. Sinambela fDP, fDarsono fPV, fHidayah fN. fPengaruh fRiwayat fPemberian fAsi fEksklusif fdengan fKejadian fStunting fPada fBalita fDi fWilayah fKerja fPUSKESMAS fTeluk fTiram fBanjarmasin. fDinas fKesehatan fJurnal fKebidanan fDan fKeperawatan. f2020;10(1):102-111. <https://doi.org/10.33859/dksm.v10i1.435>
 9. Hanifa fD. fHubungan fPemberian fAir fSusu fIbu fEksklusif fdengan fKejadian fstunting fpada fanak fusia f12-36 fbulan fdi fWilayah fKerja fPuskesmas fWonosari fI fGunung fKidul. fYogyakarta, fUniversitas f'Aisyiyah. fPublished fonline f2017.
 10. Ni'mah fK, fNadhiroh fSR. fFaktor fyang fBerhubungan fdengan fKejadian fStunting fpada fBalita. fMedia fGizi fIndonesia. f2016;10(1):13-19. <https://doi.org/10.20473/MGI.V10I1.13-19>
 11. Fatimah fNSH, fWirjatmadi fB. fTingkat fKecukupan fVitamin fa, fSeng fDan fZat fBesi fSerta fFrekuensi fInfeksi fpada fBalita fStunting fDan fNon fStunting. fMedia fGizi fIndonesia. f2018;13(2):168. <https://doi.org/10.20473/mgi.v13i2.168-175>
 12. Angkat fAH. fPenyakit fInfeksi fdan fPraktek fPemberian fMP-ASI fTerhadap fKejadian fStunting fPada fAnak fUsia f12-36 fBulan fdi fKecamatan fSimpang fKiri fKota fSubulussalam. fJurnal fDunia fGizi. f2018;1(1):52. <https://doi.org/10.33085/jdg.v1i1.299>
 13. Himawati fEH, fFitria fL. fHubungan fInfeksi fSaluran fPernapasan fAtas fdengan fKejadian fStunting fpada fAnak fUsia fdi fBawah f5 fTahun fdi fSampang. fJurnal fKesehatan fMasyarakat fIndonesia. f2020;15(1):1. <https://doi.org/10.26714/jkmi.15.1.2020.1-5>
 14. Rhamadani fRA, fNoviasty fR, fAdrianto fR. fUnderweight, fStunting, fWasting fDan fKaitannya fTerhadap fAsupan fMakan, fPengetahuan fIbu, fDan fPemanfaatan fPelayanan fKesehatan. fJurnal fRiset fGizi. f2020;8(2):101-106. <https://doi.org/10.31983/jrg.v8i2.6329>
 15. Batubara fI, fJuwarni fS. fFaktor-Faktor fYang fBerhubungan fdengan fKejadian fStunting fDi fKecamatan fSayurmatinggi fKabupaten fTapanuli fSelatan. fJurnal fReproductive fHealth. fPublished fonline f2018.